

Statement of participation

Srignana Lokesh Ezhil

has completed the free course including any mandatory tests for:

Supporting and developing resilience in social work

This free 10-hour course explored what it takes to become a resilient practitioner in social work.

Issue date: 2 November 2025

www.open.edu/openlearn

This statement does not imply the award of credit points nor the conferment of a University Qualification.
This statement confirms that this free course and all mandatory tests were passed by the learner.

Please go to the course on OpenLearn for full details:

<https://www.open.edu/openlearn/health-sports-psychology/supporting-and-developing-resilience-social-work/content-section-0>

COURSE CODE: **K315_2**

Supporting and developing resilience in social work

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Course summary

What does it take to become a resilient practitioner in social work? This free course, Supporting and developing resilience in social work, will guide you through some important concepts. An understanding of 'emotional resilience' and 'professional leadership' will help to guide you through taking a positive approach to problems that arise in social work practice. You will also be introduced to some ideas about leadership in social work practice.

Learning outcomes

By completing this course, the learner should be able to:

- discuss why emotional resilience is important in social work practice and what skills and strategies are involved
- explore the support that social workers can expect from their managers, and how to get the best out of supervision
- demonstrate a critical understanding of the skills and qualities involved in social work professional leadership
- understand the benefits of criticality, reflection and analysis to social work practice and continuing professional development.

Completed study

The learner has completed the following:

Section 1

What is emotional resilience?

Section 2

Enhancing resilience

Section 3

Engaging with professional leadership

Section 4

Supervision

Section 5

Reviewing emotional resilience